

FEATURES OF TRANSLATION OF INTERNET TERMS FROM ENGLISH INTO RUSSIAN AND UZBEK

Qodirova Madina Odiljon qizi

FerSU, a master student

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Annotation: This article is devoted to the problem of translation of complex Internet terms (including compound terms, phrases, abbreviations) from English into Russian and Uzbek.

Keywords: term, terminology, neoterm, concept, Internet, abbreviation.

INTRODUCTION

Terminology is a layer of vocabulary, a system of terms related to a particular field of production. A term is a word or phrase expressing a particular concept, and is mainly intended to express precise scientific concept. If a term is created and used by certain industry experts, and if this term expresses new meaning or notion, like a neologism, it is called “neoterm”. According to Dadabaev, “the Uzbek language in general, and its Internet terminology in particular, is like a complex sociotechnical system that works continuously and is constantly changing”.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Internet terms can be divided by their structure: “a single-core term is a simple term, and if a term contains two or more cores – it is a complex term”. The problem of translation of complex Internet terms is in their diversity of functions and content. For example, the following complex Internet terms, function to name something: “cable local-area network” – «кабельная локальная сеть» - “kabelli mahalliy tarmoq”; “card with magnetic strip” – «карта с магнитной полосой» - “magnit yo‘lli karta”; while the terms “Carrier Sense Multiple Access with Collision Detection (CSMA / CD)” – «Множественный доступ с контролем несущей и обнаружением коллизий» - “ko‘pchilik tomonidan erkin foydalanish”; “character based information system” – «Информационная система на основе символов» - “axborotning nishonli tizimi”; “classification of information and its bearers as secret” – «Отнесение информации и ее носителей к тайне» - “ma‘lumotlar va ularni tashuvchilarni maxfiylashtirish”; “Code Division Multiple Access” – “Кодовым разделением множественного доступа” - “kodli ajratishli ko‘pchilik tomonidan erkin foydalanish” function to describe. Moreover, the terms like “dual-homed gateway” – «двойной шлюз» - “ikki uyli shlyuz”; “e-development” – «Электронная разработка» - “AKT yordamida taraqqiyot”; “e-signature certificate user” – “imzo kaliti sertifikati foydalanuvchisi”; “full-text database” – “to‘la matnli ma‘lumotlar bazasi” function to define.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An analysis of the English Internet terminology of the joint form revealed that a certain group of these terms was originally formed in the general lexicon or other field terminology, and a method of “word-for-word” translation is used. For example, the term “Databank” is a combination of words “data” – “ma’lumotlar” and “bank” – “банк”, so it can be translated as “ma’lumotlar banki”. But, the term “backbone”, translated into Uzbek as “magistral”, while it is derived from the combination of “back” – “orqa” and bone – “suyak”.

The problem of translation of combinational terms has always been one of the most pressing issues in the theory of translation and in the theory of terminology. There are cases, when it is necessary to translate Internet terms consisting of 4 words: “insurance form of information protection” – “axborot muhofazasining sug’urta shakli”, “Integrated Services Digital Network” - “xizmatlari birlashgan raqamli tarmoq”, “interactive television operating system” – “o‘zaro faol teleko‘rsatuvlar operatsion tizimi” and so on.

Most of the two-component Internet terms are formed by the preposition “of”. For example, the term “minimum of privilege” - “eng kam imtiyozlar” means one of the basic principles of the organization of protection system in Internet terminology, in which each subject has the least privileges to perform the tasks assigned to him. In some cases, in the process of translation of two- component Internet terms from English into Uzbek one of the components stayed unchanged completely: “Banyan tarmog‘i”, “Internet tarmog‘i”, “Internet etiketi”, “Internet infratuzilmasi”, “Ethernet standarti”, “Internet reklama”, “Internet banki”, “Internet treyding”, “Internet futurologiyasi”, “Internet provayderi”, “Ethernet texnologiyasi” etc.

The first somponent of the two-somponent terminology may consist of asronyms: DNS server - DNS serveri, BGP protocol - BGP bayonnomasi, NSFNET network - NSFNET tarmog‘i, ISDN standard - ISDN standarti, BRI interfase - BRI interfeysi, SASE-system – SASE-tizimi.

CONCLUSION

Abbreviations is another problematis field in the tranlsation of Internet terms. They san be translated with the help of salking, semi-salking or finding equivalentents . Examples inslude “SSNET - (Somputer Ssiense NETWORK)” – “kompyuter ilmiy tarmog‘i”, “NSFNET” - (“National Ssiense Fondation NETWORK”) - “milliy fan fondi tarmog‘i”, UUSPNET (Unix-to- Unix Sopy) - “xalqaro elektron pochta”, “BASP” – (Bandwidth Allosation Sontrol Protosol) - “o‘tkazish qobiliyatini ajratishning boshqarish bayonnomasi”, “BGP” (Border Gateway Protosol) – “chegara tarmoqlararo bayonnoma”, “BIP” – (Bit Interleave

Parity) - “bitlar navbatlanishi juftligi”, or “hujjatlar uslubiyati semantikasi va spesifikasini belgilovchi til”, ets.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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